

THE QUESTION OF TRANSITION TO "GREEN" ECONOMY AND ITS MAIN LEGAL PROBLEMS

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Anatasia. In the article, the need for rational and effective use of limited resources is the main issue of the economy and a guarantee for the stabilization process of the "green economy" and its legal issues are highlighted in the article. The author's opinion and suggestions are noted in the article.

Key words: *Green economy, concept, strategy, technology, economy, sustainable development, investment, energy, anthropogenic, ecology, innovation, greening.*

INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, the idea of "Green" economy is widely discussed by world ecologists and economists. The fact that this issue is often discussed in various international political forums, on the part of state leaders and political scientists, is a sign of serious attention to the "Greening" policy. In today's rapidly developing world, human needs are increasing in unprecedented ways. It follows that humanity will increasingly turn to nature to obtain the resources it needs to meet its enormous needs. "Green economy" and "Greening" arise from the need to prevent such changes from having a negative impact on the lives of future generations and to ensure a comfortable life for them as well. If the negative impact of economic growth on nature is not prevented, it will have a serious negative impact not only on the life of future generations, but also on the current conditions of society. If humanity's attitude towards the natural environment changes, ecological culture develops, relations related to production, service and product consumption adapt to "Greening" efforts, we can hope for a promising green and prosperous future. Iadi "Green" economy is important in sustainable development as well as in ensuring population welfare and economic growth.

¹Green economy is a model of economic development that assumes a responsible attitude of people to Earth's resources. It aims to find a reasonable compromise between increasing prosperity and preserving natural resources. Economic development is accompanied by continuous growth of production and consumption.

Green economy is a model of economic development that assumes a responsible attitude of people to the Earth's resources, this model is aimed at finding a reasonable compromise between increasing well-being and preserving natural resources.

A green economy is defined as an economy that improves human well-being and ensures social justice. Important features of such an economy: efficient use of natural resources; preservation and increase of natural capital; reduce pollution; low carbon emissions; prevent the loss of ecosystem services and biodiversity; income and employment growth.

At the conceptual level, the Green economy develops the most general action strategy and defines "Green" directions in the development of the economic system. Next comes the ideological level. It should be a place where "Green" values are updated for business entities. At this level, the main task of the Green economy is to introduce the idea of the value and necessity of environmentally friendly production to the society .

After the formation of the first two levels, the necessary problem area becomes legal, state regulation and the development of relevant legislation. This is the political level of the Green Economy. It is necessary to develop legislation that ²simultaneously contributes to the "Greening" of the economy and is suitable for

¹<https://journal.sovcombank.ru/esg/chto-takoe-zelenaya-ekonomika>

²https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/%D0%97%D0%B5%D0%BB%D1%91%D0%BD%D0%B0%D1%8F_%D1%8D%D0%BA%D0%BE%D0%BD%D0%BE%D0%BC%D0%B8%D0%BA%D0%B0

business entities.

In the last fifty years, more products have been produced on Earth than during the entire period of civilization from the beginning of mankind to 1950 .

it has a negative impact on the environment . Every year, humans destroy more than 11 million hectares of forests, emit 20 billion tons of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere, and release more than 300 million tons of plastic waste. If this process is not intervened, humanity will face a global ecological disaster. The New Economic Concept was developed to overcome the conflict between economic growth and the conservation of natural resources, and this Concept is based on three axioms: in the conditions of limited space, the sphere of influence cannot be expanded indefinitely, the resources of the earth are limited, and the increase in consumption will soon exhaust them . all processes on earth are closely related to each other.

Many countries are seriously concerned about environmental problems and have developed a set of economic measures to combat negative anthropogenic impacts. Western Europe, South Korea, USA and China are leaders in this field.

Principles of green economy:

1. Principle of efficiency and sufficiency;
2. The welfare principle ;
3. The principle of good management ;
4. Reducing investments in production that harms the environment;
5. Increasing the tax burden for "dirty" industries;
6. Financial support of green industry;
7. Reduction of resource-intensive production methods;
8. Concept of green economy and sustainable development.³

³<https://journal.sovcombank.ru/esg/chto-takoe-zelenaya-ekonomika>

Anthropogenic factors are a group of factors related to the influence of man and his economic activities on plants, animals and other natural components. Man influences nature, adapts it to his needs, changes the fauna and flora in vast areas of the Earth, which leads to the reduction of vegetation, the extermination of some plant and animal species, the introduction of plants, etc. Man's indirect influence on nature is carried out by changing the climate, the physical state and chemical composition of the atmosphere and water bodies, the top layer of the earth, the structure of the soil, etc. Development of protected lands, establishment of monocultural (one-crop) agrocenoses and other activities have a great impact on the change of natural biocenoses. The problems of the development of the nuclear industry, especially the testing of nuclear weapons, the increase of industrial waste polluting water, atmosphere and soil are becoming important. Humans have to some extent created new conditions for cultivated plants and domestic animals, improved their breeds and increased their productivity, increased the yield of crops , but activities that cause disturbances in the natural balance without a deep understanding of the laws of nature can lead to unexpected negative consequences. Improper irrigation of crops leads to soil salinization and erosion, and excessive drying of land changes the vegetation cover above ground. Modern science and technology have created favorable conditions for human interaction with nature on a large scale, and environmental protection has become an important problem. So, anthropogenic factors are caused by the impact of human activity on nature.⁴

In 2012, as part of the implementation of the UN environmental program, the main principles were formed, according to which the use of land resources is limited to the extent that does not harm the restoration of natural systems, and countries support sustainable production and consumption, low carbon and

⁴https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Anthropogenic_factors

introduced resource-saving technologies.

Currently, special attention is paid to increasing the socio-economic well-being of the population, but the criteria for this should be revised, because the level of the gross domestic product is an inappropriate tool for assessing well-being, since it does not take into account the environmental factor.

Today, the need to transition to a new "Green Economy" model is undeniable. States should invest in ecological restoration and conservation of natural diversity. But this should be done carefully. Otherwise, the world will face great financial losses, socio-political problems, in addition to ecological disaster . We can see the main stages of the transition in the example of environmental initiatives implemented by the European Union. For example, the European Investment Bank will stop lending to gas projects from 2022, which in the future will deprive the industry not only of preferential loans from countries, but also reduce its attractiveness for private investors.

In 2026, the European Parliament plans to introduce a so-called carbon tax. A fee is charged for importing goods into the EU, the production of which involves large-scale emissions of carbon dioxide. European manufacturers, in turn, will lose benefits that exempt them from buying emission quotas.

As part of the Green Strategy developed by the European Commission at the end of 2019, the EU plans to allocate 260 billion euros until 2030 to prevent the consequences of climate change. The strategy includes several directions: preservation of biological diversity, reduction of emissions from transport, development of renewable energy sources, development of organic agriculture.⁵

In the last decade, the EU countries have been transitioning to a circular economy. This economic model involves the constant circulation of materials during production and consumption. When creating a new product, the company thinks

⁵<https://journal.sovcombank.ru/esg/chto-takoe-zelenaya-ekonomika>

in advance about ways to dispose of it or recycle or reuse materials.

began to be used in 1987, when it was announced in the report of the UN International Commission on Environment and Development. It is a set of measures aimed at meeting the needs of people without harming the environment. Sustainable development is possible by maintaining a balance between three main components: economic growth, social responsibility and environmental balance. The task of the green economy is to unite them and mitigate the existing contradictions.

There are several obstacles to the transition to a green economy. Implementation of new environmental principles has been slow, especially in developing countries. This sector requires significant investment by the state, which is not practiced in a number of countries.⁶

Another limiting factor is the resistance of the fuel and energy lobby. The owners of oil and gas companies are in no hurry to give up their profits and are doing everything to stop the greening process. For example, the American Petroleum Institute launched a massive information attack in the middle of the 2020 US election race. The attack was aimed at opposing presidential candidate Joe Biden's plans to curtail oil production on federal lands.

In addition to the problems listed above, there are several other problems:

- state intervention in the economy;
- increase in production costs;
- increase in tax burden;
- job cuts;
- increase in the price of products and services
- legal and protective frameworks.⁷

⁶<https://journal.sovcombank.ru/esg/chto-takoe-zelenaya-ekonomika>

⁷<https://journal.sovcombank.ru/esg/chto-takoe-zelenaya-ekonomika>

Management in the field of energy conservation is characterized by the fragmentation of functions and powers of various state bodies . Currently, a special authorized body performs certain management functions in the field of energy saving. A number of functions - control, monitoring, planning, program development - are simultaneously the powers of different state bodies (within the powers of each body). In the implementation of such a management model, the risk of repetition inevitably increases , and there is not a sufficiently clear demarcation of actions between various subjects of the implementation of powers, which cannot affect the effectiveness of the implementation of legal norms.

In its current form, the legislation cannot ensure the creation of a "Green Economy". A clear concept of the system of economic regulatory measures, which is primarily aimed at regulating not environmental, but economic public relations, is required in the legal norms of various areas of legislation. Fundamental revision and serious development of legislation on taxes and levies, banking and budget legislation, first of all, the economy contained in the legislation on environmental protection and natural resources it is necessary to strengthen and implement general legal norms for regulation, and secondly, it is necessary to properly legalize several sources of financing of environmentally significant activities.

The formation and development of the concept of "green economy" is solved by introducing these ideas into the practice of ensuring sustainable development. Sustainable development means development that does not compromise the ability to meet the needs of future generations. The economic approach to sustainable development implies the rational use of limited resources. The social approach aims to promote social stability and cultural diversity on a global scale. The ecological approach should help ensure the normal functioning of ecological

systems.⁸

The term "green economy" cannot replace the concept of sustainable development, because this theory is an important condition for achieving sustainable development. The current global economy is characterized by the following symptoms: environmental degradation (climate change, warming, loss of biodiversity), limited natural capital, increasing poverty, lack of clean water, food, energy, deterioration of economic and social relations between people and countries. For the above reasons, the world, including Uzbekistan, is considering the transition to the "Green Economy". Formation of "green economy" ensures "green growth" and serves to implement the strategy of sustainable development.

, sustainable development of the economy, development of a long-term strategy of structural changes, taking into account internal and global processes and problems It is explained by the release, depletion of limited reserves of resources, aggravation of the environmental situation. Due to the rapid development of industry, environmental pollution, water shortage and the drying up of the Aral Sea are being faced.

The low energy efficiency of the national economy, the low level of use of natural resources, the slow pace of technological innovation, and the passive participation of small business entities in the introduction of innovative solutions for the development of the "Green Economy" are obstacles. The lack of a long-term strategy in this regard does not allow the implementation of systematic measures for the introduction of "Green technologies" and the transition to the "Green economy".⁹

In order to fulfill the obligations of the Paris Agreement of October 4, 2019,

⁸<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/neobhodimost-i-prioritetnye-napravleniya-perehoda-k-zelenoy-ekonomike-v-uzbekistane>

⁹<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/neobhodimost-i-prioritetnye-napravleniya-perehoda-k-zelenoy-ekonomike-v-uzbekistane>

the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the strategy of the transition to the green economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019" was adopted.

The goal of the National Strategy is to achieve sustainable economic development that contributes to social development, reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, climate and environmental stability by integrating the principles of "Green Economy" into the ongoing structural reforms.

In the long-term perspective, the transition to "Green economy" in Uzbekistan is based on the following principles: compliance with national goals and objectives in the field of sustainable development; rational use of resources, sustainable consumption and production; inclusion of environmental and social criteria in the economic accounting system; prioritizing the use of "Green" tools and approaches to achieve the goals of socio-economic development; achieving existing macroeconomic goals by increasing competitiveness and growth rates in key sectors, creating "Green" jobs and improving the well-being of the population; ensuring the investment attractiveness of measures of effective use of economic resources.¹⁰

In the first direction defined in the National Strategy, by 2030, the goal of doubling the energy efficiency in the basic sectors of the economy is set. For this purpose, it is planned to modernize the infrastructure of industrial enterprises, increase energy efficiency by at least 20 percent by further applying clean and environmentally friendly technologies and industrial processes , increase energy efficiency in the production of automobile fuel and vehicles, and improve the environment. Uzbekistan 's goals for the "Green Economy" for 2019-2030 , expected results:

¹⁰<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/neobhodimost-i-prioritetnye-napravleniya-perehoda-k-zelenoy-ekonomike-v-uzbekistane>

- reduction of specific greenhouse gas emissions per unit of gross domestic product by 10% from the 2010 level;
- increase energy efficiency and reduce the carbon intensity of GDP; Double the size;
- further development of renewable energy sources, increasing their share in total electricity production to 25%;
- ensuring up to 100% use of modern, cheap and reliable energy supply for the population and economic sectors;
- ensuring their sustainability by modernizing the infrastructure of industrial enterprises, improving energy efficiency and increasing the use of clean, environmentally friendly technologies and industrial processes by at least 20%;
- significantly increase the efficiency of water use in all sectors of the economy, introduce drip irrigation technologies in areas up to 1 million hectares and increase the yield of crops grown in them by 20-40%;
- production of the main types of food agricultural products, increasing the average yield to 20-25%.

The second direction of the National Strategy is to diversify energy consumption and develop the use of renewable energy sources during the transition to a green economy in the country.

The third direction of the National Strategy includes the problems of adaptation and mitigation of climate change, increasing the efficiency of the use of natural resources and preservation of natural ecosystems.

The fourth direction of the National Strategy is "Development of economic mechanisms to support the green economy", "Development of institutional foundations for the introduction of green technologies", regulatory and legal framework in the field of "Green economy", "Green economy" aimed at improving the regulatory framework, "Green Economy" regulation mechanisms.

monitoring ¹¹energy efficiency, integrating the principles of "Green Economy" into education and science, increasing production capacity and creating a favorable environment for the transition to "Green Economy".

There are a number of factors that have a negative impact on the development of the Green Economy network in Uzbekistan:

- high cost of production of renewable energy sources and lower capacity compared to conventional energy sources compared to other countries . At the beginning of the 21st century , the cost of electricity generation from renewable energy sources remains high in countries with developing market economies. Uzbekistan is leading the group of countries in providing cheap electricity to the population ;
- there are no economic financial support mechanisms for encouraging the use of renewable energy sources . There are insufficient legal and organizational bases for the operation of economic mechanisms and the use of renewable energy sources.
- sufficient awareness of the population about modern types of "Green economy", "Green energy", in particular, renewable energy sources;
- one of the preventing factors affecting the scale of use of renewable energy sources is the development of nuclear energy, the cost of producing clean energy from renewable energy sources is 20 times higher than that of nuclear power plants . Based on world practice, it is necessary to develop the legal basis for the introduction of environmentally friendly product standards, their regulation and certification system.

In the long-term perspective, the priority directions for the development of financial and non-financial mechanisms for the development of the " Green

¹¹<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/neobhodimost-i-prioritetnye-napravleniya-perehoda-k-zelenoy-ekonomike-v-uzbekistane>

Economy" in Uzbekistan are as follows:

It is necessary to develop the institutional foundations of the introduction of "green technologies" , in particular, to assess the technological needs, to determine the priority tasks and to select the most advanced technologies that will help in their development. It is necessary to create organizational structures - technology supply agencies - for the commercialization of "green technologies" and the development of the economic mechanism of innovation support;

- It is necessary to improve the regulatory framework for the development of the "green economy", in particular, to develop proposals for inventory, to improve the regulatory framework covering the priorities of the National Strategy, and to implement the national system of indicators . "Green economy";

- development of energy efficiency regulation and control mechanisms, new tariffs for guaranteed purchase of electricity from newly introduced solar, wind and biogas power plants, micro and small hydropower plants with an installed capacity of up to 1 MW by regional power grid enterprises should be introduced.¹²

- Integrating "Green Economy" principles into education and science;

- Development of public-private partnership potential for the introduction of "Green technologies"; to help private investors to introduce "Green innovations"; development of mechanisms for encouraging state "Green purchases" by introducing a system of certification of energy and resource efficiency of goods; taking into account the principles of "Green Economy" in the development of state educational programs for personnel training and retraining; development of research in areas related to climate change mitigation and adaptation; strengthening cooperation between national and foreign scientific organizations in

¹²<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/neobhodimost-i-prioritetnye-napravleniya-perehoda-k-zelenoy-ekonomike-v-uzbekistane>

the field of creation of "Green technologies";

Support of "Green investments" : creation of "Green lending", "Green" savings, special energy saving funds and other similar mechanisms; Activation of the private sector in the financing of projects for the transition to "green investments", support of the sustainable growth of the economy of the "Green economy" by the state on the basis of tax-budget policy.¹³

In conclusion, the proposed measures are necessary to create legal frameworks that increase the competitiveness of the national economy and serve to move to the path of sustainable development based on the "Green Economy", "Greening" the national economy, rational use of natural resources, and a systematic solution to environmental problems . serves to form legal procedures and principles, to implement the concept of development.

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¹³<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/neobhodimost-i-prioritetnye-napravleniya-perehoda-k-zelenoy-ekonomike-v-uzbekistane>